

Organomercury complexes of sulfide-thiol ligands : X-ray structure determination of {CH₃Hg[Ph(SCH₃)C=C(S)-Ph]}

K. Hussain Reddy

Department of Chemistry, Sri Krishnadevaraya University, Anantapur-515 003, India

Fax : 91-08554-29043

Manuscript received 3 September 2001, revised 5 November 2001, accepted 28 December 2001

1-(Methylthio)-*cis*-stilbene-2-thiol, Ph(SCH₃)C=C(SH)Ph and 1-(benzylthio)-*cis*-stilbene-2-thiol, Ph(SCH₂Ph)C=C(SH)Ph form monomeric complexes with Hg²⁺, CH₃Hg⁺ and C₆H₅Hg⁺. The structure of CH₃Hg[Ph(SCH₃)C=C(S)Ph] has been determined by X-ray diffraction study which confirms its 3-coordinate monomeric structure.

In continuation of our earlier work^{1,2}, we report here the synthesis and characterization of mercury and organomercury(II) complexes with sulfide-thiol ligands, viz. 1-(methylthio)-*cis*-stilbene-2-thiol (I) and 1-(benzylthio)-*cis*-stilbene-2-thiol (II). The structure of CH₃Hg[Ph(SCH₃)C=C(S)Ph] was determined by X-ray single crystal diffraction.

Results and Discussion

All the complexes (Table 1) are stable at room temperature, non-hygroscopic, insoluble in water but soluble in chloroform and dichloromethane.

Table 1. Analytical data of ligands and their metal complexes

Compd.*	M.p. °C	Analysis % : Found (Calcd.)	
		C	H
Ph(SCH ₃)C=C(SH)Ph	67	69.50 (69.75)	5.52 (5.42)
Ph(SCH ₂ Ph)C=C(SH)Ph	61	75.40 (75.44)	5.42 (5.31)
Hg[Ph(SCH ₃)C=C(S)Ph] ₂	139	51.76 (51.06)	3.55 (3.68)
Hg[Ph(SCH ₂ Ph)C=C(S)Ph] ₂	121	47.60 (47.19)	3.20 (3.18)
CH ₃ Hg[Ph(SCH ₃)C=C(S)Ph]	99	41.10 (40.59)	3.15 (3.38)
C ₆ H ₅ Hg[Ph(SCH ₃)C=C(S)Ph]	110	46.95 (47.10)	3.42 (3.36)

*All compounds were coloured yellow.

Attempts to grow single crystals of sufficient quality for X-ray diffraction were successful only in the case of CH₃Hg[Ph(SCH₃)C=C(S)Ph].

The ¹H NMR signals, assignment (number) and shift in ppm (multiplicity) for the ligands and complexes are as follows : Ph(SCH₃)C=C(SH)Ph, phenyl (10H), 7.190–7.050 (m); CH₃ (3H) 2.141 (s); SH (1H) 4.31 (s); Ph(SCH₂Ph)C=C(SH)Ph, phenyl (15H) 7.11–7.25 (m); CH₂ (2H) 3.67 (s);

SH (1H) 4.34 (s); Hg[Ph(SCH₃)C=C(S)Ph]₂, phenyl (20H) 7.201–7.063 (m); CH₃ (6H) 2.149 (s); Hg[Ph(SCH₂Ph)C=C(S)Ph]₂, phenyl (30H) 7.284–7.012 (m); -CH₂- (4H) 3.771 (s); CH₃Hg[Ph(SCH₃)C=C(S)Ph], phenyl (10H) 7.169–7.025 (m), S-CH₃ (3H) 2.016 (s); Hg-CH₃ (3H) 0.711 (s); C₆H₅Hg[Ph(SCH₃)C=C(S)Ph], phenyl (15H) 7.361–7.024 (m), S-CH₃ (3H) 2.099 (s).

The crystallographic data collection details for CH₃Hg[Ph(SCH₃)C=C(S)Ph] are given in experimental section. The molecular structure is shown in Fig. 1 and the important bond lengths and bond angles are listed in Table 2.

Fig. 1. Perspective drawing of CH₃Hg[Ph(SCH₃)C=C(S)Ph] with numbering of atoms.

Table 2. Selected bond lengths (Å) and angles (°) for $\text{CH}_3\text{Hg}[\text{Ph}(\text{SCH}_3)\text{C}=\text{C}(\text{S})\text{Ph}]$

Hg-S(1)	2.375(3)	S(1)-Hg-S(2)	77.70(8)
Hg-S(2)	2.953(3)	S(1)-Hg-C(16)	168.9(3)
Hg-C(16)	2.07(1)	S(2)-Hg-C(16)	112.9(3)
S(1)-C(1)	1.763(9)	Hg-S(1)-C(1)	110.1(3)
S(2)-C(2)	1.78(1)	Hg-S(2)-C(2)	97.9(3)
S(2)-C(15)	1.815(9)	Hg-S(2)-C(15)	119.1(4)
C(1)-C(2)	1.36(1)	C(2)-S(2)-C(15)	101.7(4)
C(1)-C(3)	1.50(1)	S(1)-C(1)-C(2)	129.1(7)
C(2)-C(9)	1.46(1)	S(1)-C(1)-C(3)	109.3(6)
C(3)-C(4)	1.39(1)	C(2)-C(1)-C(3)	121.5(8)
C(3)-C(8)	1.39(1)	S(2)-C(2)-C(1)	120.1(7)
C(4)-C(15)	1.38(1)	S(2)-C(2)-C(9)	115.5(7)
C(5)-C(16)	1.37(1)	C(1)-C(3)-C(9)	124.3(8)
C(6)-C(7)	1.37(1)	C(1)-C(3)-C(4)	119.7(8)
C(7)-C(8)	1.38(1)	C(1)-C(3)-C(8)	121.8(9)
C(9)-C(10)	1.40(1)	C(4)-C(3)-C(8)	118.4(9)
C(9)-C(14)	1.40(1)	C(3)-C(4)-C(5)	120.3(9)
C(10)-C(11)	1.39(1)	C(4)-C(5)-C(6)	120.8(9)
C(11)-C(12)	1.38(1)	C(5)-C(6)-C(7)	119.4(9)
C(12)-C(13)	1.40(1)	C(6)-C(7)-C(8)	120.4(9)
C(13)-C(14)	1.36(1)	C(3)-C(8)-C(7)	120.7(9)
		C(2)-C(9)-C(10)	121.0(9)
		C(2)-C(9)-C(14)	120.9(8)
		C(10)-C(9)-C(14)	118.1(8)
		C(9)-C(10)-C(11)	119.7(9)
		C(10)-C(11)-C(12)	121.4(9)
		C(11)-C(12)-C(13)	118.7(9)
		C(12)-C(13)-C(14)	120.7(9)
		C(9)-C(14)-C(13)	121.5(9)

The complex, $[\text{CH}_3\text{HgPh}(\text{SCH}_3)\text{C}=\text{C}(\text{S})\text{Ph}]$ consists of a Hg metal centre bonded to one carbon atom and two sulfur atoms. The sulfur atoms of the ligand form a five-membered ring to Hg with bite angle of 110.1(3) and 97.9(3)°. Fig. 1 reveals that mercury is three-coordinate. Hg-S(1) is short compared to Hg-S(2) bond length. Consequently the 5-membered ring formed in the complex is unsymmetrical. The methyl group of mercury is inclined towards the S-CH₃ group.

A comparison with structures of other monomeric mercury(II) thiolates², shows that Hg-S bond distances of the present complexes Hg-S(1) = 2.375 (2) and Hg-S(2) = 2.953 (3) suggest the presence covalent bonds. The covalent bond distance between Hg and S(1) is within the expected range and is not perturbed by the presence of methyl group on Hg. However, the methyl group is slightly inclined towards the SCH₃ group. The phenyl rings of the ligand are not in a near parallel (or coplanar) arrangement with each other suggesting no interaction between the aromatic rings.

The present structure is interesting since it is a novel three-coordinate mercury(II) complex. Few complexes of three-coordinate complexes of mercury exists. Examples are $[\text{Hg}(\text{SR})_3]^-$, where R = Ph³, C₆H₂Pr₃⁴, Bu⁵.

The study shows that the anions of present facultative bidentate ligands form even 3-coordinated complexes with mercury (with larger ionic radius) under the condition where zinc and cadmium (with smaller ionic radii) reached a higher coordination of 5 and 6, respectively^{1,2}.

Experimental

Solvents used for the preparation of thiols and their mercury(II) complexes were redistilled and dried. All other chemicals were of A.R. grade and used as supplied.

1-(Methylthio)-*cis*-stilbene-2-thiol and 1-(benzylthio)-*cis*-stilbene-2-thiol were prepared respectively by the reaction of $\text{Ni}[\text{Ph}(\text{SH}_3\text{C})\text{C}=\text{C}(\text{S})\text{Ph}]_2$ and $\text{Ni}[\text{Ph}(\text{SCH}_2\text{Ph})\text{C}=\text{C}(\text{S})\text{Ph}]_2$ with alkaline NaCN by following methods described earlier^{1,6}.

Mercury complexes : Mercury(II) chloride (0.27 g, 1 mmol) dissolved in water (30 ml) was added dropwise to hot ethanolic solution (2 mmol; 100 ml) of 1-(1-methylthio)-*cis*-stilbene-2-thiol (0.52 g)/1-(benzylthio)-*cis*-stilbene-2-thiol (0.66 g). The yellow coloured solid formed immediately was crystallized from CH₂Cl₂-hexane solvent pair.

$\text{CH}_3\text{Hg}[\text{Ph}(\text{SCH}_3)\text{C}=\text{C}(\text{S})\text{Ph}]$: A mixture of hot ethanolic solution (30 ml) of 1-(methylthio)stilbenethiol (0.25 g, 1 mmol) and methylmercury(II) hydroxide (0.23 g, 1 mmol) was refluxed for 1 h. It was then cooled and kept in the refrigerator overnight. The orange yellow coloured crystalline product formed was washed with ethanol and hexane and crystallized from CH₂Cl₂-hexane (1 : 1) solvent pair to give crystals suitable to carry out X-ray diffraction studies.

$\text{C}_6\text{H}_5\text{Hg}[\text{Ph}(\text{SCH}_3)\text{C}=\text{C}(\text{S})\text{Ph}]$: A mixture of equimolar ethanolic solution (30 ml) of 1-(methylthio)stilbenethiol (0.5 g, 2 mmol) and phenylmercury(II) chloride (0.63 g, 2 mmol) was refluxed for 1 h. The light yellow coloured product obtained on cooling was crystallized from CH₂Cl₂-hexane (1 : 1) solvent pair.

The ¹H NMR spectra (CDCl₃) were recorded in sealed tubes with a GE-300 NMR instrument at 300 MHz.

X-Ray crystallography :

Crystal data : HgS₂C₁₆H₁₆, formula weight = 473.01, monoclinic, space group C2/C (# 15), *a* = 31.360 (5), *b* = 6.376 (3), *c* = 16.320 (2) Å, β = 111.45 (1)°, *V* = 3037 (2) Å³, *Z* = 8, *D*_{calc} = 2.069 g/cm³, *F*(000) = 1792, μ (MoKα) = 103.80 cm⁻¹.

Measurements were made on a crystal of approximate dimensions (0.250 × 0.250 × 0.150 mm) with a Rigaku AFC6R diffractometer and graphite monochromated Mo-

K α radiation ($\lambda = 0.71069 \text{ \AA}$) using ω - 2ϕ scan mode, scan rate $32.0^\circ/\text{min}$ (in ω), scan width $(1.31 + 0.30 \tan \phi)^\circ$. No significant decay, Lorentz and polarization corrections were applied (*trans* factors : 0.82–1.25).

The structure was solved using the heavy-atom procedure and refined via full-matrix least squares method using TEXSAN programs. The mercury and sulfur atoms were located from the Patterson map. Successive different - Fourier syntheses and full matrix refinements revealed all other hydrogen atoms. Hydrogen atoms were constrained to their calculated positions using a riding model and refined with fixed isotropic temperature factors. All other atoms were refined anisotropically. Least-square weight of the form $4F_o^2/\sigma^2 (F_o^2)$ was applied. The final different - Fourier synthesis was essentially featureless, longest difference peak 1.12 e\AA^{-3} largest hole -1.70 e\AA^{-3} . The final data parameter ratio was 10.481 : 1, $R = 0.032$, $R_w = 0.037$.

Acknowledgement

The author thanks C.S.I.R., New Delhi, for financial

support. The author also thanks Prof. G. N. Schrauzer, University of California, San Diego, USA, for his interest in this work.

References

1. Z. Cheng, K. Hussain Reddy, E. O. Schlemper and G. N. Schrauzer, *Inorg. Chem.*, 1990, **29**, 4100.
2. K. H. Reddy, Z. Cheng, E. O. Schlemper and G. N. Schrauzer, *Inorg. Chem.*, 1992, **29**, 1673; G. N. Schrauzer, Z. Cheng, K. H. Reddy and E. O. Schlemper, *Chem. Ber.*, 1993, **126**, 1337; K. H. Reddy and Y. Lingappa, *Transition Met. Chem.*, 1994, **19**, 487.
3. E. S. Gruff and S. A. Koch, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 1989, **111**, 1883; 1990, **112**, 1245.
4. G. Christou, K. Folting and J. C. Huffman, *Polyhedron*, 1984, **3**, 1247.
5. S. P. Watson, J. G. Wright, F. M. MacDonnell, J. W. Bryson, M. Sabat and T.V. O'Holloran, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 1990, **112**, 2824.
6. G. N. Schrauzer, Z. Cheng and E. O. Schlemper, *Inorg. Chem.*, 1990, **29**, 3371.